

CURRENT STATE OF PREVENTION OF PRESSURE AND VIOLENCE AGAINST WOMEN

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Abstract: The article is dedicated to the current state of harassment and violence against women and the measures being taken to prevent it. The study examines various forms of violence, their social, economic, and cultural factors. The prevalence of violence against women, existing problems in society, and the role of the state, non-governmental organizations, and the public in their elimination are analyzed.

Keywords: Women, harassment, violence, prevention, current situation, social factors, legislation, public, prevention, non-governmental organizations, education.

Organizational and legal support for the activities of the subjects of prevention of harassment and violence against women serves the effectiveness and development of this system. For this, it is necessary to pay attention to the following issues: first, to clearly and correctly distribute the tasks and functions of sectoral state bodies and civil society institutions in this area; second, to achieve the prevention of harassment and violence by all subjects in harmony with their main activities within the limits of the powers established by law; third, to specialize them in the implementation of measures for the general and victimological prevention of offenses; fourth, to implement the activities of subjects through the introduction of new methods and forms, information and communication technologies.

The fundamental reforms aimed at improving the system of subjects of prevention of harassment and violence in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Protection of Women from Harassment and Violence"[1]: the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, local government bodies, internal affairs bodies, labor bodies, state education management bodies and educational institutions, state healthcare management bodies and healthcare institutions, the State Committee for Family and Women, self-government bodies of citizens, non-governmental non-profit organizations and other civil society institutions, in turn, serve to effectively organize the implementation of the main tasks and functions assigned to them by current legislation, including measures for the prevention of harassment and violence.

In order to ensure the effective organization of the prevention of harassment and violence against women in the process of large-scale reforms carried out in our country, 29 republican, regional, and inter-district model centers for the rehabilitation and adaptation of women have been created, including 1 Republican Center, 14 regional centers, and 14 inter-district model centers. Also, through the redistribution of staff in cities and districts, 356 positions of senior prevention inspectors for working with women were introduced, and 89 staff units of psychologist positions were introduced into internal affairs bodies in areas with a difficult criminogenic situation;

- the practice of protecting women from various types of harassment and violence, implementing operational measures in this regard, organizing targeted preventive work with

victims[2], issuing protection orders to victims of harassment and violence[3] has been organized;

The State Committee for Family and Women was created, whose activities were reorganized to implement targeted measures to protect the rights and legitimate interests of women, ensure guarantees of gender equality, provide socio-legal and psychological assistance to families and women in difficult social situations, and strengthen spiritual and moral values in the family.

- a completely new system of targeted state support for women and young people in need of social protection, citizens in difficult living conditions, unemployed and without a profession, in need of legal and moral-psychological support has been introduced[5].

To provide emergency assistance to victims of harassment and violence, a continuous operation of the "hotline" with the short number 1146 was established[6].

- In order to ensure the employment of women included in the "Women's Notebook," to strengthen the health of women, they were provided with employment and assistance in acquiring a profession.

- further strengthening the system of social protection of women, strengthening their health, creating the necessary conditions for girls to receive education and upbringing, educating talented and educated girls and increasing their scientific potential, increasing the socio-economic and political activity of women, strengthening their role in society, in particular, in public administration, and ensuring gender equality[8].

Organizational support for the prevention of harassment and violence against women through the full and effective implementation of these measures will contribute to: a) the constant service of internal affairs bodies, the mahalla institute to the people, turning them into true supporters and allies of the population, increasing their role and significance; b) supporting segments of the population in need of social and legal protection, strengthening their place in society, strengthening guarantees for the protection of their rights and legitimate interests; c) forming a healthy and stable socio-spiritual environment in society, mahalla, and family; d) fundamental reform of organizational and legal mechanisms for ensuring peace, harmony, and tranquility in administrative territories; e) identifying and strengthening targeted preventive work with women who have found themselves in difficult social life situations, whose families are unstable, and who are subjected to harassment and violence; f) establishing continuous, systematic cooperation of crime prevention subjects with other state bodies and civil society institutions.

Reforms in the system of internal affairs bodies are not fully and effectively implemented in all regions, and the newly created and reorganized structural subdivisions as a result of the reforms are not effectively using the existing opportunities created for the targeted and high-quality implementation of crime prevention, in particular, victimological prevention of offenses[9].

After all, no state body can ensure the effectiveness of its activities only within its internal capabilities without organizing cooperation with other structures. The subjects of crime prevention also cooperate with the network services included in the system, other law enforcement agencies, state and public organizations in the implementation of the tasks assigned to them[10].

The organization of the prevention of harassment and violence against women is carried out on the basis of the powers and requirements established by the Law of the Republic of

Uzbekistan "On the Prevention of Offenses"[11], the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Prevention of Neglect and Offenses among Minors"[12], the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Protection of Women from Harassment and Violence"[13] and other legislative acts on the protection of women from harassment and violence, as well as the obligations and rights established by the Law "On Internal Affairs Bodies"[14].

Analysis shows that in most cases, on the one hand, women suffer from domestic offenses, and minors - from violence by their parents or persons replacing them, and on the other hand, in the chain of causes and conditions for the commission of these acts, their behavior, lifestyle, immorality, ignorance, and antisocial behavior occupy a special place.

Therefore, the prevention of offenses against women by internal affairs bodies, each of their sectoral services, in particular, the prevention of offenses, firstly, based on the requirements of the laws specified in the current legislation, secondly, to identify and eliminate the causes and conditions for the formation of a predisposition to becoming victims in them, thirdly, to warn and protect them from offenses, harassment and threats, fourthly, to inform them about the possibilities and methods of protecting themselves from offenses, harassment and threats, requires the implementation of spiritual-educational, pedagogical-rehabilitation, legal and other comprehensive measures in conjunction with other general, special and individual measures.

Today, the cooperation of the subjects of crime prevention in the prevention of harassment and violence against women is ensured, firstly, through the mutual exchange of information necessary for carrying out this activity between the subjects implementing and participating in preventive measures, and secondly, through joint preparation and implementation of preventive measures.

Analysis of practice shows that the interaction of crime prevention entities, in particular, the prevention services of internal affairs bodies, with citizens' self-government bodies on the prevention of harassment and violence against women in administrative territories is not carried out at the proper level. These entities commit serious and especially serious crimes due to insufficient targeted preventive work with dysfunctional families in the administrative territory, identifying women in difficult life situations, and women subjected to harassment and violence.

In order to ensure the implementation of the requirements of paragraph 5 of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Measures for Further Improvement of the System of Crime Prevention and Combating Crime"[15], mobile courts are organized every Thursday within the framework of "Crime Prevention Day," public discussion of offenses committed within the framework of family and domestic relations in the administrative territory, and the application of effective appropriate punitive measures to the perpetrator are of great importance in the early prevention of the above-mentioned crimes of premeditated murder. Indeed, one of the urgent issues to be solved in society today is the prevention and protection from harassment and violence against women.

It should be noted that in preventing harassment and violence against women, crime prevention service prevention inspectors carry out targeted and systematic preventive measures in this direction. In particular, they will take comprehensive measures to ensure prompt awareness of the situation regarding individuals and families affected by violence and harassment living in administrative territories, to ensure early prevention of potential

conflicts, to improve the socio-psychological environment in troubled families, and to carry out legal awareness and propaganda work among the population.

In conclusion, it should be noted that in the implementation of general prevention of crimes within the framework of violence and harassment in administrative territories, it is necessary, first of all, to ensure the rights and freedoms of the individual, to peacefully resolve conflicts arising in family and domestic life, to strengthen the spiritual and moral environment in families, especially to conduct awareness-raising work among the population to raise the legal awareness and legal culture of citizens, to identify, study, take measures to eliminate the causes and conditions contributing to offenses and crimes within the framework of violence and harassment, as well as to prevent family divorces, to organize interaction with the sectoral services of internal affairs bodies, civil society institutions and the general public.

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